

**THE EFFECTS OF PRICING STRATEGIES ON CONSUMERS' BEHAVIOURAL
PATTERN AND PURCHASE DECISIONS**

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ABSTRACT

This study was mainly undertaken with the motive of understanding the existence of a proportional relationship between consumer behaviour and pricing strategies employed, given the role of other factors in the decision-making process such as the social media, brand name, compulsive urge of a buyer to buy a product and so on. The hypotheses were tested using questionnaires (G-forms). The data pooled reveal different perspectives of consumers and the way each of them perceive and understand a product's price change. The quantitative results were analysed and mathematically interpreted using the relevant statistical tools. Customers vary their buying pattern both in terms of quantity and type whenever there is a price change. The results also show that most of the customers in today's market are well informed and have a very good understanding of select pricing strategies applied by businesses.

KEY WORDS

Marketing, Pricing, Pricing strategies, Consumer behaviour, Consumption and buying pattern, Proportional relationship, Consumer perspectives and perceptions, informed, price change.

INTRODUCTION

Marketing has increasingly become one of the integral professions of the 21st century. The reason has a lot to do with the concept of *Caveat Venditor* i.e., let the seller beware. During the industrial revolution, the product and its quantification was given much importance. Later the quantity was replaced by quality which had price as the important and underlying factor. Then came the selling and promotional era followed by the marketing era. We are now in the societal, value based, integrated, environment friendly marketing era. But still the fundamental aspect of the subject holds primary significance. The marketing mix still have a strategic importance on the fortune of a product and the company that produces it. The only thing that has changed is the style of marketing. Before and even now profit making is the prime goal but it is now integrated along with customer value addition and retention followed by environmental vigilance.

Due to the quick changes in economic and technical conditions, today's consumers are more inquisitive, knowledgeable, and aware of what he or she wants. Compared to the different sorts of disaggregate pricing methods that are used to market items as positively as possible, this is relevant for consumer goods. Most of the time, the little prices for these consumer goods are paid all at once. It is risky to believe that customers find a given pricing approach to be fair; in addition, it is inappropriate to claim that customers think the price that is established reflects the cost of manufacturing a good. Price is the sum of the values that consumers exchange for the benefits of owning or using a product or service. It can mean different things to different people; for example, it can be interest to lenders, service fees to lenders, insurance premiums to insurers, transportation costs to transporters, honoraria to guest lecturers, etc. The level of information and the number of brand comparisons increase in proportion to how important pricing is in purchasing choices. The fundamental fact is that customers who often make purchases come into touch with pricing more frequently. The selection of a price objective and related strategy is a crucial responsibility of the business owner and a crucial step in the planning process. It involves more than just figuring out the cost of production. Every firm involved in the production of consumer goods and services must have a pricing strategy since it provides information about the company and its products. A company does not establish a single price but rather a pricing structure that encompasses several things in its line. It is one of the most essential components of the marketing mix since, unlike the other components, it is the only one that brings in money for the company. In compared to the other components of marketing strategy, price is the most flexible since pricing choices may be put into practice rather fast. It can figure out a company's market share and profitability. Understanding consumer behaviour is also an integral part in the process of price fixation and maintenance. But as stated earlier and even again in the further chapters, buyers today are very well informed and make their own strategic purchase decisions w.r.t the strategies employed by different businesses.

As a result, allocating the assignment of a price or pricing to a product or range of items is a strategic operation that will be having an effect on how customers perceive the company's offerings and estimate its foreseeable future purchases. However, how pricing actions work is less obvious and influenced by the marketing idea. Certainly, customers would want to spend less. Businesses ought to look beyond the methodology of fixing prices they feel is apt for a product having estimated cost and profit still relevant but no longer sufficient and acknowledge that equalization of the way they generate revenue can open up opportunities to create additional value. Traditional pricing strategy is by definition incapable of harmonious associations. However, it needs to become a more socially conscious, collaborative exercise. This study analyses how these strategies are taken by the consumers and how it affects their buying behaviour. A lot of emphasis is given to understand the relationship between select pricing strategies and the buyer purchase decision in par with the same.

HYPOTHESES

H1: Pricing strategies in any form affects the consumer's buying decision and pattern to some extent ranging from high to low.

H2: Consumers today are well informed and are able to identify the pricing strategies employed by various producers.

H3: Consumers change or at least try to change their buying pattern and quantum as they become aware about the pricing strategies employed by business giants.

H4: Social media sources help consumers to understand the psychological pricing strategy employed by businesses to enlarge their sales.

H5: Consumers cannot stop or restrict their purchase of some particular products even though they can understand the strategies employed by the businesses and that they are overpriced.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

If effective product development, promotion and distribution sow the seeds of business success, effective pricing is the harvest. Firms successful at creating customer value with the other marketing mix activities must still capture some of this value in the prices they earn. Pricing decisions are usually challenging but are especially vexing in periods of rapidly changing costs and market uncertainty. The price the company charges will fall somewhere between one that is too low to produce a profit and one that is too high to produce any demand. Customer perceptions of the product’s value set the ceiling for its price. If customers perceive that the product’s price is greater than its value, they will not buy the product. Likewise, product costs set the floor for a product’s price. If the company prices the product below its costs, the

company's profits will suffer. In setting its price between these two extremes, the company must consider several external and internal factors, including competitors' strategies and prices, the overall marketing strategy and mix, and the nature of the market and demand.

Price is the pivot of an economy. If effective product development, promotion and distribution sow the seeds of business success, effective pricing is the harvest. A study on effects of pricing strategies showed that consumer's changes their perspective of seeing different products on basis of the price and competitors' price of the same category of products. The study has also shed light to many pricing strategies and purchase decision processes¹. Hence it is important that businesses employ their pricing strategies with due considerations as it acts as a key variable in financial modelling, which determines the revenues realized, the profits earned, and the amounts reinvested in the firm's development for its long-term survival. Many business organizations struggle when it comes to pricing a product, which leads to price wars². Therefore it must be employed by considering customer satisfaction and profit optimization as two sides of the same coin. The results of a study on pricing goals show that the companies under investigation in the present study appear to adhere to a hierarchy of pricing objectives, with their primary emphasis being on the retention of current clients and the acquisition of new ones to ensure their long-term survival in their market, while keeping financial concerns and goals in mind³. In order to achieve this, companies these days employ a series of pricing strategies like dynamic pricing, Behavioural Pricing, Psychological Pricing, Price Skimming etc.

A study has shown that there are two dimensions of **PEP (personalized dynamic pricing)** - price individualization level and segmentation base. It was found out that segment pricing is fairer than individual pricing, but firm has to adapt the suitable PEP according to the consumer's perspective⁴. **Behavioural pricing** is a relatively new approach in the pricing of commodities. A study examined how firms make BBP decisions when consumers do not observe whether they practice BBP. They find that BBP increases firm profits but decreases consumer surplus and social welfare for both firms and consumers⁵. A **psychological pricing** is the regular application of human innumeracy in marketing and sales. Businesses take advantage of people's lack of interest in numbers through psychological pricing tactics. Several instances of psychological pricing are examined in an essay by Richard Branson, published in The New York Review of Books⁶. According to research, psychological patterns like representativeness, product availability, and anchoring heuristics, as well as sociodemographic factors like age, income, education, gender, lifestyle, family size, reference groups, and social roles and status, are major determinants of consumers' purchasing decisions⁷

It was pointed out that consumer innovators charge lower prices than firms for comparable games and that consumers and firms show different inclinations in aligning prices with the games' development costs and perceived quality. The subsequent interview study with 29 hobbyist game developers provides clear support for the motivational explanations of consumers' pricing decisions. It showed how **price skimming** is a technique in seeking attention from the customers⁸. Premium pricing means setting the price of products high. The **premium pricing** strategy creates an approving perception among buyers because buyers believe that the higher the price of goods better will be its quality. A quantitative research method to find the relationship between premium pricing strategy and customer retention at

international hotels in the sample area revealed that there is a positive and significant association between premium pricing strategies and customer retention at selected international hotels⁹.

An effective pricing strategy such as value-based pricing strategy and cost-based pricing strategy that takes into account both organisational objectives and target consumers perceptions and sensitivities would improve an organization's marketing effectiveness according to a study on telecommunications companies in Port Harcourt¹⁰. Similarly, strategies like **price promotion**, where products are sold at discounted price is also proved to be an effective tool. A sample survey to examine the impact of price promotions on the process of immediate purchase of goods in Isfahan has been conducted for 384 people who were customers of Hyper Star store. The results came out as price promotions had a positive effect on impulsive buying behaviour and pricing promotions had an effect on service innovation¹¹.

Pricing plays more important role to consumers than other attributes like location, product designs etc. in their buying decision. A study on consumers purchases choices when location and cost are provided showed that location partially has slight impact on customer purchase decisions, but pricing does. For small and medium-sized enterprises to be able to provide more competitive rates, these results are anticipated to be a beneficial source of information and recommendations¹². As a result, setting the right prices for your product is a balancing act. That's because numbers behave in a logical way. Humans, on the other hand can be way more complex. The efficient use of reason and intuition can be facilitated by selecting the appropriate pricing team design. Pricing team intuition is functional for high degrees of product innovativeness and dysfunctional for low levels, whereas price team rationality has an undeniably favourable effect on pricing strategy efficacy¹³. Complexity in consumer behaviour sets the need to analyse them to employ the right pricing strategy. According to prior research's statistically significant findings, it is concluded that psychographic factors often have an impact on customers' intentions to purchase private label whereas perceptual factors primarily affect consumers' attitudes regarding private label¹⁴.

Findings from an experiment with a designed shopping task using natural stimuli reveal that an enhanced label design with unit price leads to an increase in the number of eye fixations. This is an interesting finding of factors affecting consumer decisions¹⁵. Consumer demand, competition and cost over the past decade have created pricing opportunities and challenges. Competition forces to adapt and apply less aggressive pricing strategy and charge less as per the guidelines of retailers in developing a coherent pricing strategy. New forms of competition (from adjacent markets, discount outlets, resale stores and the sharing economy); changes in consumers' shopping habits across different channels and technological changes (including the pervasiveness of mobile services) affect retailer pricing¹⁶. Due to the advancement of technology, findings conclude to a number of new advancements in pricing methodology. The findings also point to a continued emphasis on consumer markets and economic theories¹⁷. We all know that Internet is a pool of information. It provides access to all kinds of information to transform a consumer to a price informed one. In a study, the moderating impact of buying intentions are taken into account as it studies the impacts of unfavourable reviews on customer pricing perception and subsequent purchase behaviour. According to the results drawn from

the trials, customers with purchase intent are more negatively impacted by the percentage of bad reviews than are consumers that do not have purchase intent¹⁸.

The emergence of Internet product sales platform has provided space for counterfeit products and relevant fraudulent signal strategies. With the continuous development of e-commerce sector, more and more consumers do shopping via the Internet. The study on the performance and pricing strategy of Internet counterfeiting has important practical significance¹⁹. The authors found that the adoption of social media as a strategic tool provides a platform to promote tactical revenue management strategies and to practice different pricing motives²⁰. The firm's sales volume and earnings are directly impacted by pricing choices and strategies. A pricing approach only considers the kind of information that is utilised to establish product prices. It is the strategy used by businesses to set prices for both goods and services. To determine the most appropriate price, an efficient pricing strategy is required²¹. An analysis on the impact of price planning in FMCG (Fast moving customer goods) sector and its importance on the behaviour of consumer's behaviour proposed a methodological framework, to identify various principles of pricing policy which would have a huge impact on the decisions related to the pricing of FMCG commodities²². Pricing decision is one of the major decisions for any marketer. For consumers, having the ability to compare prices is the second most important benefit of purchasing online. An effective pricing strategy can help the business cater to its target customers and defend its products from the competition²³.

Pricing strategies and Buyer behaviour can be seen as two different conceptual areas from the above study. One of the basic aims and a hypothesis of this project is to establish a relationship between the two. By reading the above framework, the hypothesis and the research model of the project, it must be clearly understandable now as to how to relate pricing strategies and buyer behaviour. This section is followed by a review of related literatures and an inferential and retrospective study on the agenda. Pricing strategies do have a direct or an indirect impact on every consumer's buying decision. In fact, the reason behind the usage and application of different pricing strategies is to influence the buyer's purchase decision on a particular product.

Any pricing technique or strategy will somehow influence a consumer's purchase decision. But the actual matter of consideration is, how much? To what extent? These will be assessed by a series of statistical and inferential analysis on the data collected. By using pricing strategies networks, marketers can learn how to engage with customers on their own terms, and pricing strategies platforms can provide consumers with valuable tools to connect, link, and interact with the marketers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A survey was conducted among the undergraduate students studying in a private university in Vellore. Engineering, Commerce, Agriculture, Business and students of various other streams belonging to the age group of 17 to 24 were selected for the survey. Primary data were collected through survey using questionnaire. A set of questions pertaining to the research and its objectives was prepared and circulated among the respondents through various electronic platforms like E-mail, WhatsApp, Instagram and Facebook.

Sample definition

Responses were collected from 100 respondents. The institution selected for the study consists of students across the country which is not a common factor in all other institutions in Vellore or in any other institution in Tamil Nadu. This can be considered as one of the advantages of the sample. It is very diverse and represents a wider population. If the same study is done in any other institution in Vellore, the results may vary. Every respondent seemed to have a very different approach in answering and the variance obtained is showing the sample's way of approach and observation of pricing strategies and their reaction/adaptation of the same.

Tools and Techniques

The type of research used is associative, where the aim is to find out the relationship between variables. The sampling technique in this study is purpose sampling. This is done when the number of respondents is unknown and the number is obtained on a random selection. The number obtained by random selection is 100 and it was a mix of different students with different courses and ideas. The outcomes will be obtained using standard deviation test, test of variance and correlation analysis performed on the data collected using IBM SPSS software V.25.1.

Sample Characteristics

Designation	Students, PhD scholars and young entrepreneurs
Age	17-25
Area	VIT University, Vellore
Ethnicity	Indian (mostly)
Employment status	Interns, PhD scholars and short-term employees
Marital status	Unmarried
Attributions	Strictly Gen Z
Income class	Middle and Sophisticated

	Engineering students	Non-Engineering students	Total
Male	24	28	52
Female	18	30	48
Total	42	58	100

Collection of data

The data was collected by virtually circulating a google form with questions intending to prove our hypotheses. The number of responses were limited to 100. The data collection was done between the 2nd and 4th of November, 2022. The target sample was only selected for responses.

The following were the questions asked

1.	Do pricing and pricing strategies employed by businesses affect your purchase?
2.	Telecommunication companies usually price their products cheap or free of cost to a certain period of time (like Jio). And many platforms like Spotify offer one-month free subscription to certain range of consumers. Do you think this kind of pricing strategy will have an impact on your buying decision? Is your buying pattern influenced by such strategies?
3.	Given a decent knowledge of a product's pricing strategy, to what extent will that affect your purchase decision? Rate.
4.	Are you aware of the pricing strategies employed by your favourite brands?
5.	Choose an option that best describes a pricing strategy that advocates higher initial

:

9.	Social media's role in pricing strategies and buying decision. 1. Increases one's level of knowledge about pricing strategies. 2. Affects one's buying decision. Choose you what you think is true.
10.	You are going to purchase a new car. Before the purchase, you do research about the model over the internet, look at the vehicle in person, go through all the details and decide to buy that vehicle. You come across a video by a renowned vlogger on YouTube giving a negative review of your desired vehicle. Now on a scale of 1 to 5, how much of your decision will be affected or changed?
11.	Suppose you have decided to buy an Apple iPhone 14 pro Max which costs around 150000 and in the store, you notice a newly launched mobile that you have never heard of, costing 95000. The specifications are similar and the design is good. Which one will you buy?
12.	Which of the following do you think will supersede the pricing strategies employed by a company and will positively influence your buying decision?
13.	Do you mind paying huge money for a very premium product, irrespective of its pricing strategy given its brand power is extremely high.

DATA INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS

The survey done among 100 select respondents almost revealed the much-expected outcome, yes pricing strategies and their knowledge about them have an influence on their buying pattern and quantum. The following results were analysed with respect to individual hypotheses.

H1: Pricing strategies in any form affects the consumer’s buying decision and pattern to some extent ranging from high to low.

95% of the respondents agreed that given the sufficient knowledge about pricing strategies, their consumption pattern will vary. A real-life case was given as an example, the pricing strategy followed was pointed out and about 88% of the respondents agreed that they will shift consumption in a way that’s beneficial and economic to them. Thus, pricing strategies have an impact on consumer’s buying decision. The degree of variation is high when the products are

low ended and of less price and quality and opposite when the products are dearer and carry esteem. Thus, H1 is accepted.

H2: Consumers today are well informed and are able to identify the pricing strategies employed by various producers.

Choose an option that best describes a pricing strategy that advocates higher initial price and lower price in the later periods.

Choices	Responses (%)
Penetration pricing	8
Price skimming	68
Price riding	4
Idk	20

Bata shoes generally prices their product to the nearest lower ‘9’ digit figures (e.g: Instead of Rs 300 it is priced Rs 299). Have you come across such pricing strategies? If yes identify the type of strategy used.

Choices	Responses (%)
Price skimming	10
Premium pricing	6
Geographical pricing	2
Psychological pricing	70
Idk	12

About 70% of the respondents were able to identify the pricing strategies employed by various businesses and given a real case the percentage is a little higher. Use of jargons and complicated pricing policies are the barriers that affect customer knowledge here. Anyhow most of the customers have the required amount of information and knowledge to identify pricing strategies and apply the same in their consumption. Thus, H2 is accepted.

H3: Consumers change or at least try to change their buying pattern and quantum as they become aware about the pricing strategies employed by business giants.

The respondents were given a case where they come to know a positive and customer friendly pricing strategy and also a negative and unscrupulous strategy. The responses were used to calculate correlation and variance to obtain the degree of changes made by them in their buying pattern.

	No change	Less than before	Shift to another brand	Shift and ask your friends to do the same
Positive	18	02	46	34
Negative	08	05	16	71

The statistical analysis infers a positive correlation of 0.451. This means that the respondents change their buying pattern as they get to know about the pricing strategies employed by businesses and the type of impact that poses on them. Thus, H3 is accepted.

H4: Social media sources help consumers to understand the psychological pricing strategy employed by businesses to enlarge their sales.

Given a situation of decision making where the respondents were asked to assume that a youtuber, a renowned vlogger gives negative reviews for a product that they had already decided to buy. 16% agreed to immediately cancel the plan of purchases, 78% decided to relook the product and however shift to some other product, most likely the one recommended by the youtuber. For a question like:

Social media's role in pricing strategies and buying decision.

- Increases one's level of knowledge about pricing strategies.
- Affects one's buying decision.

Choose you what you think is true.

Choices	Responses (%)
1 only	3
2 only	12
Both 1 and 2	79
Neither 1 nor 2	6

A test of variance was run. A Standard deviation of 36.194 and thus, a variance of 1310.000 was obtained. This shows the unanimous answer given by the respondents, “Both 1 and 2”. 79% think that social media increases one’s knowledge of pricing strategies and thus impacts a buyer’s decision. Thus, H4 is accepted.

H5: Consumers cannot stop or restrict their purchase of some particular products even though they can understand the strategies employed by the businesses and that they are overpriced.

	Yes	No	
iPhone Vs. Cheaper substitute	83	17	
Overpriced Products	85	15	

With the given number of responses, 83% prefer iPhones instead of cheaper phones with similar specifications. Given the higher quality and brand name, 85% are okay buying overpriced products. As the data is collected from Gen Z respondents, this result is quite expected and acceptable.

A Chi-square test was run and a significance of 0.6997 was obtained, which is clearly more than 0.05, the significance level. Thus, the relation between iPhones and other overpriced products are independent and not proportional. H5 is accepted independent of the significance value as the variance obtained (2178, 2450) are clearly high and show the preference of luxurious products by the respondents irrespective of the price.

CONCLUSION

The whole study emphasizes on the relation between pricing strategies and buyer behaviour with respect to the strategy employed. The results obtained clearly show that there is a positive, a very direct relationship between the two variables. Customers today also have a decent knowledge of the pricing strategies employed by the business (88%). Customers change or tend to change their consumption pattern or quantum and vary their choices of brand as they come to know about the strategies employed by the businesses. There is also a direct relationship in this shifting behaviour of customers, given a positive or negative strategy (Correlation – 0.451). Social media plays a vital role in the education of customers and prospective buyers about the pricing strategies. It even has a very significant impact on a customer's final purchase decision. Customers are ready to buy products priced using premium pricing strategy, given it has the top brand value and provides intangible credits like social esteem and trend sync. Luxurious and overpriced products have an elastic demand usually, which lend towards the inelastic when it provides quality (77% agree), brand name (73% agree), social esteem gained (62% agree), customer service (69% agree) and a cheaper maintenance cost with cheaper accessories (65% agree). Hence, pricing strategies are proved to be a very integral component that influences buyer behaviour either directly or implicitly.

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